

COMBINED SOLAR-FIRED CONVEYOR-CHAIN DRYING INSTALLATION FOR MELON DRYING

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The drying industry is one of the most energy-intensive sectors of the food processing industry. The continuous increase in energy consumption in this area, especially for drying high-moisture agricultural products such as grapes, melons, apples, and others, necessitates not only the rational and economical use of traditional fuel resources (gas, coal, oil, electricity, etc.) but also the search for and development of new alternative and renewable energy sources. Among these, solar energy plays an important role in the context of Central Asian countries due to its accessibility and environmental friendliness.

The use of air-solar drying methods in open areas or solar dryers is limited and dependent on climatic conditions, as well as hygienic issues. Therefore, in recent years, scientific efforts have been focused on creating energy-saving drying technologies using combined (hybrid) solar-fuel drying installations. Based on an analysis of existing drying methods and dryer designs, the authors proposed their own concepts for modernizing and optimizing the drying process as well as energy supply. The developed combined solar-fuel drying installations integrate the use of both solar energy and conventional energy sources, including electricity.

Processing agricultural products requires significant energy expenditure. The most energy-intensive process is the drying of high-moisture and sugar-rich products such as grapes, melons, figs, pears, apples, and others. For example, to produce 1 kg of dried product from various raw agricultural materials, it is necessary to remove 4.2–8.5 kg of moisture, which in terms of heat corresponds to 10,000–21,500 kJ. The efficiency of many drying installations used in the fruit and vegetable drying sector does not exceed 55%.

These data highlight the urgent need to increase the energy efficiency of drying installations through the use of advanced engineering and technological methods, recovery of heat from exhausted drying agents, and optimization of drying modes [1–2].

In this regard, to intensify the drying process of agricultural products, we developed a multi-pass dryer design that operates both on conventionally generated heat from an electric heater and on heat from solar radiation absorbed by the blackened surface of the dryer body. The structural features of the drying installation are illustrated in the figure.

Figure. Diagram of the Combined Conveyor-Chain Drying Installation

The combined conveyor-chain drying installation for melon drying (Figure) consists of a closed drying chamber (1) with a loading-unloading hatch (2), inside which a chain conveyor (3) is installed. The conveyor is driven by an electric motor (4) through a worm gearbox (5) and a chain drive (6) [3-4].

The drying chamber is divided by horizontal partitions (7) and a vertical partition (9) into conditional sections along the path of the chain conveyor and the drying agent. For suspending melon slices (9), a rod (10) with grooves is provided, which can be made of wood or plastic.

Below the lower horizontal partition (7), paired infrared (IR) emitters (11) with reflectors (12) are installed. The drying installation is equipped with a fan (13), an electric heater (14), and a ring-type heat regenerator (15). To prevent the chain (3) from derailing from the driving sprockets (16) and to ensure even tension distribution, the worm gearbox is symmetrically positioned relative to the support pillars [5-6].

Operation Principle The melon is peeled and cut into ring-shaped slices perpendicular to its axis, with a width of 15–20 mm. The slices (9) are then threaded onto the rods (10) with a spacing of 20–25 mm. With the hatch (2) open and the chain conveyor (3) moving intermittently, the prepared rods are loaded into the drying chamber (1) and fixed on both sides with hinged clamps made of spring steel [7].

Once the chain conveyor is fully loaded, the hatch is closed, the fan (13) and electric heater (14) are turned on, and the conveyor is set to continuous operation. To intensify the drying process, the IR emitters (11) with reflectors (12) are activated.

During continuous operation, the melon slices are exposed to a flow of hot air supplied by the fan (13) through the electric heater (14). In the initial drying stage, infrared rays reflected from the emitters act on the hanging melon slices. Directed IR radiation disrupts the quasi-stationary structure of the plant material and promotes moisture evaporation.

As the product moves through the multi-pass labyrinths of the drying chamber, it is intensively subjected to convective drying. The exhausted drying agent, along with evaporated moisture, passes over the upper horizontal partition (7) and enters the vertical channel bounded by the vertical partition (8) and the chamber wall (1). The relatively low-potential, moist exhaust air enters the ring-type regenerator (15) and heats the incoming fresh air, which is further heated in the electric heater (14) to the required temperature and directed under the lower horizontal partition where the IR emitters are installed.

At the end of the drying cycle, the rods with partially dried melon are removed through the hatch (2) under intermittent conveyor motion, and new rods with fresh melon slices are loaded in their place. The looped slices of dried melon are then removed from the rods, inspected, and sent to storage. After drying, the rods are washed, residues of sticky melon removed, disinfected, and prepared for reuse.

The multi-pass design of the drying chamber ensures full utilization of the thermal energy of the drying agent and increases the overall thermal efficiency of the installation. It was observed that during simultaneous exposure to hot air flow and infrared radiation, all melon slices dry uniformly. In the second drying stage, the IR emitters can be turned off, as the dried surface layers slow the moisture release from the inner layers [8–9].

If the outer casing of the drying chamber is made from galvanized sheet metal with a selective “black nickel” coating, the solar energy absorption can reach high efficiency, allowing the installation to operate under sunny conditions. In this case, a significant amount of heat from solar radiation is absorbed on the front surface facing the sun, reducing the energy consumption of the primary heat source. Thus, the proposed drying installation, due to its mass and dimensional design, demonstrates high specific productivity per unit of occupied useful area, compactness, and ease of operation.

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